

Diving into the blue: Synthetic methodologies toward aggregation induced fluorescent peptide materials.

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Fluorescence spectroscopy proved to be a powerful tool to investigate complex biological processes, such as the interactions of a protein with other proteins as well as with nucleic acids. However, fluorescent techniques show weak or quenched emission in the aggregate stage or in highly concentrated solutions due to the aggregation-caused quenching effect (ACQ). Unlike to ACQ fluorophores, aggregation induced emissive (AIE) luminogens show bright emission in the aggregate state. AIE is a photophysical phenomenon in which molecular aggregate exhibits stronger emission than a single molecule. Thus, continuous efforts are made for the design and synthesis of unnatural amino acids with various aggregation induced emissive moieties fluorophores that could easily and successfully incorporate into peptide sequences. In the present work L-phenylalanine was used as a chiral template for the preparation either in liquid or on solid phase of unnatural amino acids, that will bear a tetraphenylethene (TPE) moiety on their side chain. TPE is a classic aggregation induced emissive (AIE) molecule widely used as a fluorescent probe¹ and could easily build on L-phenylalanine via Suzuki-Miyaura cross coupling reactions. The morphology of the new fluorescent phenylalanine analogues was characterized by SEM microscopy and DLS analysis, whereas fluorescence spectroscopy assays were performed to investigate the fluorescence properties of aggregates in solid state and in solution.

Figure 1. Synthesis of TPE-based AIEgens (A) in liquid phase and (B) on solid phase; (C) Example of aggregates in different ratios of organic solvent/H₂O (water is increasing from left to right); (D) SEM analysis.

References

1. W. Chen, C. Zhang, X. Han, S. H. Liu, Y. Tan and J. Yin J. Org. Chem. (2019), 84, 14498.

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